

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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FORMATION OF A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONDITIONS OF URGENCY OF ECOLOGICAL AND CLIMATE CHANGE PROBLEMS

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УСЛОВИЯХ АКТУАЛЬНОСТИ ПРОБЛЕМ ЭКОЛОГИИ И ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ КЛИМАТА

Sarabekova Marjona Yadgor kizi

sarabekovamarjona36@gmail.com

Abraev Mamarasul Salimovich

mamarasulabraev1@gmail.com

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Abstract: In this article, ecological structure is studied as a direction of development of "green" economy. The importance of ecotourism in environmental protection and rational use of natural resources, the issues of effective use of ecotourism potential of regions in the formation of "green" economy are analyzed. There are also proposals and conclusions on the development of the field.

Абстрактный: В данной статье экологическая структура рассматривается как направление развития «зеленой» экономики. Анализируется значение экотуризма в охране окружающей среды и рациональном использовании природных ресурсов, вопросы эффективного использования экотуристского потенциала регионов в формировании «зеленой» экономики. Также есть предложения и заключения по развитию месторождения.

Key words: Ecological tourism, ecotourism, "green" economy, "green" growth, environment, natural resources, recreation.

Ключевые слова: Экологический туризм, экотуризм, «зеленая» экономика, «зеленый» рост, окружающая среда, природные ресурсы, рекреация.

Nowadays, climate change and environmental problems related to it are manifested at the local, regional and global levels and pose urgent tasks to humanity. The most important of these is the introduction of environmental requirements in the

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economy, that is, the transition to a "green" economy. Nowadays, climate change and environmental problems related to it are manifested at the local, regional and global levels and pose urgent tasks to humanity. The most important of these is the introduction of environmental requirements in the economy, that is, the transition to a "green" economy. According to foreign experts, in order to transition to a "green" economy, there are 10 environmental skills that are common in various fields of production, namely: design, leadership qualities, management skills, energy, urban planning, landscape design, communication, travel, waste management, purchasing and financial skills are in high demand. In the Strategy of the transition to a "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period of 2019-2030, approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4477 of October 4, 2019, there is a strategy for adapting to and mitigating the consequences of climate change, increasing the efficiency of the use of natural resources, and protecting natural ecosystems. a number of tasks are presented. Also, the 15th goal of the National goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development in the period until 2030 is "Protect and restore terrestrial ecosystems, promote their rational use, rational use of forests, combat desertification, stop and reverse land degradation, and the process of biodiversity loss." "stop". This, in turn, is related to the effective use of the tourist and recreational opportunities of the regions and the development of ecotourism. Today, the development directions and prospects of ecotourism are formed in connection with the laws of nature and the stability of geosystems. The natural and climatic conditions and recreational resources of our country provide an opportunity to develop ecological tourism in accordance with each region. Today, attention is paid to the organization of ecotourism in protected natural areas. For information, it should be noted that in our country there are 6 state reserves, 1 complex (landscape) order reserve, 5 state national nature parks, 11 state natural monuments, 12 state order reserves, 1 state nature nursery, 2 state biosphere reserves. , 1 national park, as well as 71 forestry farms and 5 hunting farms. In the conditions of the formation of the "green" economy in Uzbekistan, the main directions of the development of ecological tourism are as follows:

- 1) development of ecotourism master plans based on the natural conditions and capabilities of each region in our country;
- 2) wide involvement of "green" investments in ecotourism;

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- 3) Improvement of tourism infrastructure in "Chorvoq" free tourist zone, "Zomin" tourist and recreational zones;
- 4) attract the attention of foreign and domestic tourists to major ecotourism sites in our country;
- 5) ensuring employment of the population and reducing poverty by rationally using the natural conditions and resources of the regions;
- 6) use of tourist maps and signs using digital technologies in ecotourism sites;
- 7) paying serious attention to environmental protection in ecotourist places and strengthening environmental control in this regard.

On May 30, the head of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev participated in the second international summit "Green growth and cooperation for global goals - 2030" held in the form of a video conference in Seoul, the capital of Korea. Regarding the issues within the framework of the summit, the head of state noted in his speech the important directions of the updates being carried out in the country in the field of "green" recovery and expressed his point of view regarding the prospects of international cooperation in this regard. At this meeting, the issues of achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals and fulfilling the provisions of the Paris Agreement on Climate took a special place. The Strategy of the transition to a "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period of 2019-2030 was adopted. On this basis, work is carried out systematically. The main goal of the strategy of the transition to a "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019-2030 is to integrate the principles of the "green" economy into the structural reforms implemented in the country, to achieve a solid economic development that allows for social development, reducing the level of greenhouse gas emissions, and climate and ecological stability. is to achieve.

In conclusion, ecological tourism has a high role and importance in Uzbekistan's transition to a "green" economy and in the implementation of national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development. There is still a lot of work to be done in this direction, which develops in harmony with nature, and there are many untapped opportunities. In this regard, development of ecotourism as an important branch of the "green" economy, formation of the ecotourism image of our country by attracting advanced foreign experiences and innovative technologies to the field is one of our main tasks.

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